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Guidance document for cross sectorial proficiency testing

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1. Summary

Proficiency testing (PT) or external quality assessment (EQA) is an integrated part of quality assurance management in veterinary, food and public health laboratories. The CARE consortium have developed suggestions for the design and execution of new cross sectorial proficiency testing schemes within the field of isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens, typing/characterization including whole genome sequencing (WGS) and outbreak surveillance based on WGS data (cluster detection). This guidance document for cross sectorial PT/EQS is based on the experiences gained by conducting pilot PTs/EQAs within the three areas an input from the partners that participated in the project. The conclusion of the guidance report can be summarized:

- EQAs/PTs are pivotal for laboratory quality management and an important tool to ensure the quality of laboratory and *in silico* based results.
- Repositories of reference material, that reflects the current epidemiological situation, are needed to organize efficient EQAs/PTs.
- The current EU supported EQA/PT schemes can be further developed and designed so they cover the whole OH sector and accommodate WGS based methods.
- The development of new EQA/PT schemes should be coordinated and the responsible national and international bodies should provide the adequate resources.
- The strategy for using EQA/PT schemes and the results of the schemes should be reviewed and assessed periodically and adjusted accordingly.

2. Guidance for cross sectorial genome sequence based PTs.

Proficiency testing (PT) or external quality assessment (EQA) is an integrated part of quality assurance management in veterinary, food and public health laboratories. The CARE consortium have developed suggestions for the design and execution of new cross sectorial proficiency testing schemes within the field of isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens, typing/characterization including whole genome sequencing (WGS) and outbreak surveillance based on WGS data (cluster detection). This guidance document are based on input from the partners that participated in the project and the experiences gained by conducting pilot PTs/EQAs within the three areas.

National and international surveillance systems are more reliable if the collected and generated data from the human health, food, animal and environmental sectors are comparable. This includes all aspects of how the data are generated and includes information on collection approach, sample types, typing schemes, analytical approach communication, reporting and use of the results in a collaborative one health (OH) context.

The participation in proficiency testing (PT) or external quality assessment (EQA) is an integrated part of the quality management in a laboratory, as well as fulfilling the requirements if the laboratories are following the guidelines for quality management stipulated in the ISO 15189: medical laboratories - requirements for quality and competence or ISO 17025: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories.

Participation in PTs/EQAs enables laboratories to assess the quality of their analytical methods and take appropriate action if the quality is unsatisfactory. PTs/EQAs further enables comparison of laboratory results between participants. An important obligation of the EU reference laboratories (EURL) and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) is to ensure the validity

and comparability of data produced within EU on human and animal pathogens and antimicrobial resistance by conducting regular EQAs/PTs. The organization of EQAs/PTs are also a part of the obligations for National reference laboratories. However, these PTs/EQAs are designed to meet the sector specific requirements and might not be suitable for assessing the data comparability and other needs across OH sectors.

The EU commission are supporting several networks of EURLs for various microorganisms and antimicrobial resistance. The commission funds the EURLs serving the food and veterinary sector, whereas ECDC supports the established public health networks like the European Food and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses Network (FWD-Net). ECDC does not currently have reference laboratories but offers EQAs using a tendering process where the EQA services are provided by a contractor.

The European PT/EQA activities is sector specific in the way that the EURL are focusing on the organization of PTs/EQAs within their field of competences, e.g. Salmonella, Campylobacter etc., and the ECDC are focusing its efforts to meet the needs in the public health sector also tendering based on species or antimicrobial resistance. It is clear that there is some redundancy in the area in the way that some of the PTs/EQAs could serve as cross sectorial PTs/EQAs. This is particularly evident for many of the new generic methods that are based on DNA-technology, and includes both DNA-based detection methods and the use of WGS for characterization purposes.

WGS-based methods is increasingly used within the field of food, human and animal microbiology, for characterization of pathogens including analytical approaches that can predict virulence factors, antimicrobial resistance, clonal relationship and identify food- and water borne outbreaks. WGS is also applicable for culture-free identification of a range of pathogens in complex sample material, including clinical, environmental and food samples.

PCR-based methods are also widely used and so it could be possible to organize cross sectorial PT/EQAs for the detection of specific genes. Examples could be detection of different variants of the stx genes in Shiga toxin producing Escherichia coli (STEC) and detection of different variants of genes encoding antimicrobial resistance. Such PTs/EQAs could assess if the methods applied in the different sectors are able to detect the genes that are associated with human diseases or important for the treatment with antimicrobials. Other examples of cross sectorial PT/EQAs could be sample materials with a known number of copies of featured genes that are pathogen specific.

From a quality assurance perspective, the constant rapid emergence of new generic and often proprietary based methods are a challenge because of the intrinsic conflict between standardization and onboarding/implementation of new and complex methods. WGS-based analytical approaches and the associated bioinformatics tools for analyzing the sequence data, represent another new area where new PTs/EQAs should be developed, as participation in PT/EQA schemes are an efficient way for laboratories to demonstrate that new DNA/WGS based methodologies are suitable for the purpose.

Thus, future directions for PTs/EQAs include supporting new technologies and identifying ways of doing so. The technologies typically consist of different components e.g. for WGS, a testing process includes DNA purification, library preparation and sequencing (wet laboratory processes) and the bioinformatics pipeline using in silico methods for WGS data analysis (the dry bench process). Each stage can be assessed independently using PTs/EQAs, but the whole testing process must function correctly to provide a valid result. Moreover, the diversity between laboratory processes for each stage makes methods-based PT more suited to the in silico stage of the assays than the traditional analyse-specific PTs e.g. for detection of specific pathogens in sample material.

The generic nature of WGS based methods calls for the implementation of a new generic paradigm for the organization of PTs/EQAs that can be used by laboratories that are working within the fields of DNA based detection methods and WGS.

In order to conduct valid PTs/EQAs there is a need for repositories of reference material that includes well defined live microbiological cultures, DNA preparations, and whole genome sequences. The repositories should be updated periodically and encompass reference material that reflects the current epidemiological status within each of the area that the PTs/EQAs should cover. The expenses of operating the repositories can be substantial, and therefore it could be beneficial to collaborate internationally in establishing and maintaining the repositories.

There is also a need to develop more efficient reporting and feedback platforms. Currently much of the reporting WGS-based results are uploaded manually. This is cumbersome, with increased scope for human error during the uploading of data. The feedback to the participants should be prompt, enabling the participants to take immediate actions i.e. implement corrective actions following unsatisfactory PT/EQA results. The reporting and feedback platforms should be able to accommodate different types of PTs/EQAs, as the scope of the PTs/EQAs will vary considerably.

Normally, PT involves laboratories testing the same samples performing the same test or test type and comparing the results. However, for WGS, there are many potential variations in the analytical set up, and despite this, it can still be possible to obtain the correct and anticipated result. In most cases it will still be important to consider whether the method is fit for its purpose when evaluating the results from PTs/EQAs. And, importantly, the PT/EQA provider must always strive to offer the participating laboratories the tools that allows them to take qualified decisions about their testing practices.

The establishment of novel WGS-/DNA-based PTs/EQAs requires a multidisciplinary approach and will require skills from both a laboratory analytical aspect as well as programming and computational aspect. Benefits to be gained are global as these new tools are applicable worldwide and therefore it is important that the work is undertaken internationally. Once the new PT/EQA schemes are developed and successful pilots have taken place, they should be made available for subscription by laboratories from the different sectors. Data produced from these exercises shall be managed by the respective PT/EQA providers, followed by periodic scheduled reviews and assessments coordinated and performed by partners across these sectors. It is important to underline that the work undertaken by the different stakeholders is coordinated and supported by the responsible national and international bodies by means of resources.